

An Assignment of Sociology (Research Trends)

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Development in Sociology –

Sociology began undergoing significant development in 20th century. Scholars who established sociology as a legitimate social science were careful to distinguish it from biology and psychology, fields that had also begun to generalize about human behavior. They did this by developing specific methods for the study of society. By positing a causal direction of social influence (from group to individual), Emile Durkheim gave a much-needed framework to the new science of sociology which is known as “Functionalism”.

Functionalism emphasizes a societal equilibrium. If something happens to disrupt the order and the flow of the system, society must adjust to achieve a stable state.

According to Durkheim, society should be analyzed and described in terms of functions. Society is a system of interrelated parts where no one part can function without the other. After World War 2 many universities developed large research organizations that spurred important advances in survey research application, measurement, and social statistics. The struggle over the meaningful use of statistics and theory in research began at this time. Functionalism underwent some modification when sociologist Talcott Parsons along with Robert K. Merton and others build an approach, called structural-functional analysis.

Sociology and other disciplines –

Sociological specialties were enriched by contact with other social sciences, especially political science and economics. Political sociology, for example, studied the social basis of party voting and partisan politics, spurring comparison of decision-making processes in city, state, and national governments. Econometric methods were also introduced from economics. Coleman's Foundations of Social Theory (1990), based on economic models, suggests that the individual makes rational choices in all phases of social life.

Research in Sociology -

The standard practice of research in sociology is to collect data from or about individuals, categorize their social characteristics into "groups," and relate them to other categories of individuals such as income classes, occupations, and age groups. In the early 20th century, Symbolic Interaction theory became famous. It argued that humans interact with things based on meaning ascribed to those things, the ascribed meaning of things comes from our interactions with others and society and the meanings of things are interpreted by a person when dealing with things in specific circumstances.

William I. Thomas and Ellsworth Faris used symbolic interaction theory by using personal documents, life histories, and autobiographies. The two revealed how people attach meanings to their experience and to the broader social world. The most sophisticated small-group research was devised by Erving Goffman in *The Presentation of Self in Everyday Life* (1959). Goffman insisted that the most meaningful individual behaviour occurs in the chance, intimate encounters of each day. These encounters include greeting people, appearing in public, and reacting to the physical appearance of others. Such encounters have structures of their own that can be researched by carefully constructing the “frames” (points of reference) people use to interpret and “stage” interactions. The structures are thought to represent true reality as opposed to the artificially constructed concepts that sociologists impose on the subjects they study.

Since World War II, sociology has exported much of its theory, methodology, and findings to other divisions of the university. The study of human relations and formal organizations was transferred to business schools. The study of socialization, institutions, and stratification was absorbed by departments of education. Economists widened the scope of their research by introducing social variables to the analysis of economic behaviour.

Methodological development in sociology -

Much 19th-century sociology had no system for gathering and analyzing data, but over time the inadequacies of speculative methods became increasingly evident, as did the need for obtaining reliable and verifiable knowledge. Like his contemporaries, Herbert Spencer assembled vast stores of observations made by others and used these to illustrate and support generalizations he had already formulated.

Early exploitation of statistical materials, such as official records of birth, death, crime, and suicide, provided only moderate advances in knowledge. Data were easily manipulated, often to support preconceived ideas. At the beginning of the 20th century, interest in developing a sociological methodology grew steadily. W.I. Thomas and Florian Znaniecki's systematically gathered data through letters, diaries, life histories, and other relevant documents. Significant advances in scientific methodology occurred in the 1920s. Hypotheses were developed during the research rather than being imposed a priori (a practice later replaced by theoretically guided research). Ecological method such as urban mapping was developed. Experimental methods, once limited to the domain of psychologists and considered inapplicable to social research, were eventually applied to the study of groups. Robert F. Bales at Harvard systematically observed interaction in small artificial groups, producing useful results that were replicated elsewhere. Statistician Karl Pearson's "coefficient of correlation," introduced an important concept for measuring associations between continuous variables without necessarily defining the nature of the connection. Later, statistical estimates of causal

relations were probed by “multiple regression analysis,” employing techniques that estimate the degree to which any particular variable influences a particular outcome. Method called Sociometry, introduced by J.L. Moreno in the 1930s, collects and tabulates information on group interactions.

Data Collection –

The data may be gathered by direct observation, interviews, or questionnaires. Steps must be taken to collect valid data. In face-to-face interviewing, it may be necessary to consider the interviewer’s sex or race, appearance, manner, and approach. Questions must be posed in a way that does not influence the response. Interviewers must have steps for handling resistance or refusal. Sampling errors and bias both constitute a continuing concern, especially since so much sociological knowledge is derived from samples of a larger universe. Where bias cannot be controlled, its extent may sometimes be estimated by various methods, including intensive analysis of smaller samples. Possibilities for errors arise in every stage of research, and the methods for reducing them constitute a continuing program of study in sociology.

Status –

In America, The American Sociological Society was organized in 1905, to be followed by a large number of national, regional, international, and specialized sociological organizations. These groups institutionalized the subject and continue to guide its directions and define its boundaries. Eventually in 1949 the International Sociological Association

was established under the sponsorship of UNESCO. The rapid increase of full-time sociologists, along with the growth of sociology publications, allowed the content of the discipline also to expand rapidly. By 1970 there were more than a dozen important sociological journals like *American Journal of Sociology* and an indefinite number of minor journals worldwide. Along with this growth came a flourishing of research institutions.

In France, after 1945 a strong revival of interest in sociology took place, during which the French government established a number of research institutes in the social sciences parallel to those in the natural sciences, including several in Paris—notably the *Centre d'Études Sociologiques*. These government-funded institutes employ many full-time sociologists, some of them among the more prominent scholars in the nation.

In Germany, sociology had a strong base in the late 19th century and afterward, and the writings of Tönnies, Weber, George Simmel, and others had an international impact. By the early 1930s, however, official Nazi hostility had impeded German sociology's development, and by the time of World War II the Nazis had destroyed sociology as an academic subject.

The nations of the Soviet bloc were also periodically inhospitable to sociology, but the strong interest of younger scholars alleviated some of this opposition, and in the second half of the 20th century, sociology made considerable

progress in Hungary, Poland, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia.

Little by little, sociology has penetrated some of the less-developed nations. A number of African universities have formed departments, and the subject is gaining in importance in the Philippines, India, Indonesia, and Pakistan.

Current Trends –

Applications of sociology is spreading in several directions. Many sociologists are employed by national and international bodies to recommend programs, evaluate their progress and effects, gather data for planning, and propose methods for initiating change. Sociologists aid industry by obtaining data on clients and workers. Some of this work includes social surveys, offering advice on personnel or public relations problems, providing labour unions with advice. Sociological data are now being computer analyzed by means of a variety of sophisticated procedures, to produce results that reflect the intricacy of social life. Computers also are being used to conduct simulations of social processes based on mathematical models and to collect the data for analysis.

Social Scientists are not only writing about how to apply computers, but are designing and developing new software. Some of the most popular statistical software packages, e.g., SPSS (Nie, Bent, and Hull 1975), were developed by social scientists. In recent years, social media has created an entirely new area for sociological research. Social media offers a new avenue for human interaction, creating new behaviors for sociologists to study. Various Social networking

sites like Facebook and Twitter allows society to maintain relationships on a global scale with instant access to family and friends as well as people around the world. Social media demonstrates human need to interact. Social media also enables user to form bond related to common cause and organize social and political events.

5 Known Sociologists –

1. Max Weber –

Maximilian Karl Emil Weber (21 April 1864 – 14 June 1920) was a German sociologist, historian, jurist, and political economist. He was born in Prussia (now in Germany). He gave the Social Action Theory. He also formulated the three-component theory of stratification. All of his works were written in German. Some of his works are General Economic History, Sociology of the state, Economy and the society.

2. Emile Durkheim-

Emile Durkheim (born April 15, 1858, Épinal, France—died November 15, 1917, Paris), French social scientist who developed a vigorous methodology combining empirical research with sociological theory. He is widely regarded as the founder of the French school of sociology. By 1886, as part of his doctoral dissertation, he had completed the draft of his *The Division of Labour in Society*, and was working towards establishing the new science of sociology. Durkheim was a major proponent of structural functionalism. Along with Herbert Spencer, he was one of the first people to explain the existence and quality of different parts of a society by reference to what function they served in maintaining the quotidian (i.e., by how they make society "work"). His major works were *Suicide*, *The Division of labour in society*, *The Rules of Sociological method*.

3. Herbert Spencer-

Herbert Spencer (27 April 1820 – 8 December 1903) was an English philosopher, biologist, anthropologist, and sociologist. He was born in England. Herbert Spencer is famous for his doctrine of social Darwinism, which asserted that the principles of evolution, including natural selection, apply to human societies, social classes, and individuals as well as to biological species developing over geologic time. He developed a theory of two types of society, the militant and the industrial, which corresponded to this evolutionary progression. Militant society, structured around relationships of hierarchy and obedience, was simple and undifferentiated; industrial society, based on voluntary, contractually assumed social obligations, was complex and differentiated. His work includes *Social statics*, *The principles of Sociology*, *The man versus the state*.

4. Harriet Martineau –

Harriet Martineau (12 June 1802 – 27 June 1876) was an English social theorist often seen as the first female sociologist. She was born in England. Martineau's key contribution to the field of sociology was her assertion that when studying society, one must focus on all aspects of it. She emphasized the importance of examining political, religious, and social institutions. By studying society in this way, she felt, one could deduce why inequality existed, particularly that faced by girls and women. In her writings, she brought an early feminist perspective to bear on issues such as race relations, religious life, marriage, children, and home (she herself never married or had children). She wrote many books including *Society in America*, *How to observe- Morals and Manners*, *Life in the Sickroom*.

5. Talcott Parsons –

Talcott Parsons (December 13, 1902 – May 8, 1979) was an American sociologist of the classical tradition, best known for his social action theory and structural functionalism. He was born in United States of America. In 1930, he was among the first professors in its new sociology department at Harvard University. In 1951, Parsons published two major theoretical works, *The Social System* and *Toward a General Theory of Action*. He died in Munich, Germany. His major books include- *The Social System*, *The structure of social action* and *Social structure and personality*.